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Initial Report on Occupational Studies

Deliverable Report

D8.5

WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

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In addition, there are number of experts who have contributed to the planning of the chromate study, preparation of SOPs, or are involved in the conduct of chromate study or the systematic reviews described in this report.

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3 List of abbreviations

BPA	Bisphenol A
BPF	Bisphenol F
BPS	Bisphenol S
Cr(VI)	Hexavalent chromium
DEHP	Diethylhexyl phthalate
DIDP	Diisodecyl phthalate
DINCH	1,2-Cyclohexane dicarboxylic acid diisononyl ester
DINP	Diisononyl phthalate
DPHP	Di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate
EBC	Exhaled breath condensate
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HDI	Hexamethylene diisocyanate
ICI/EQUAS	Inter-laboratory Comparison Investigation/ External Quality Assessment Scheme
ICP-MS	Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
MDI	Methylene diphenyl diisocyanate
Mn	Manganese
MN	Micronucleus
Ni	Nickel
1-OHP	1-hydroxypyrene
OEL	Occupational exposure limit
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PBL	Peripheral blood lymphocytes
PFAS	Perfluorinated alkylated substances
SOP	Standard operating procedures
TDI	Toluene diisocyanate

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4 Abstract/Summary

Occupational studies under HBM4EU aim to collect EU-relevant data on work-related exposures to prioritised substances using harmonised methods and questionnaires. Hexavalent chromium was identified as the first subject for a targeted occupational study since, on one hand there was a clear regulatory need for occupational exposure data and, on the other hand, there was the need to test new, more sensitive methods for biomonitoring. Hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) is an occupational carcinogen that has been shown to cause lung cancer in humans. Exposure to Cr(VI) may occur for example in welding activities, in Cr(VI) electroplating and other surface treatment activities. Altogether 8 countries volunteered to participate the study on chromate exposure. During 2018 harmonised methodology for the collection of biological (urine, blood and exhaled breath) and industrial hygiene samples were developed. In addition to chromium analysis, samples are collected also for the analysis of PFAS, Ni and Mn (where relevant) and effect markers (genotoxicity and epigenetics markers). In the beginning of February 2019, samplings are under way and some of the samples have been already analysed. Most of the countries are expected to finalise samplings in March 2019. The analysis of the urinary and blood (red blood cell) chromium and PFAS samples waits for the completion of ICI/EQUAS for chromium. Study is expected to be completed by the end of 2019.

In the same time, preparatory work for the next targeted occupational study is under way. This includes review of the available data on the occupational exposure to diisocyanates, phthalates, bisphenols and PAHs. This will help us to focus the following study which has been tentatively planned to be targeted on plastics and construction sectors and include diisocyanates, phthalates and bisphenols. First conclusions from these reviews are presented in this report.

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5 Introduction

The aim of task 8.5 concerning targeted occupational studies is to bridge the gaps in our knowledge of occupational exposure in different occupations or tasks when compared to other exposure sources. This means that EU-relevant data on work-related exposures to prioritised substances are collected in critical occupations using harmonised methods and questionnaires. The data is used to estimate the exposure and risks and to evaluate and identify good practices to control the exposure.

Examples in which there might be a need for targeted EU-wide occupational studies include exposure to bisphenols replacing bisphenol A, exposure to authorised chromates in chrome plating, phthalates and their substitutes in plastics industry, industrial exposure to specific aniline derivatives and diisocyanates as well as to e.g. exposure to new pesticides. Hexavalent chromium was identified as the first subject for a targeted occupational study since, on one hand there was a clear regulatory need for occupational exposure data and, on the other hand, there was the need to test new, more sensitive methods for biomonitoring.

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6 Targeted occupational study on hexavalent chromium

6.1 Background on chromium(VI)

Hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) is an occupational carcinogen that has been shown to cause lung cancer in humans. Exposure to Cr(VI) may occur for example in welding activities, in Cr(VI) electroplating and other surface treatment activities. Cr(VI) is currently a subject for regulatory actions both under the European regulation (EC 1907/2006) concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and EU Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (CMD, EC, 2017).

According to REACH legislation all companies using Cr(VI) compounds have to apply for authorisation for their uses. More than 100 authorisations for different uses of chromates have already been requested, some of these covering hundreds of workers (<https://echa.europa.eu/applications-for-authorisation-previous-consultations>). REACH concerns only the use of Cr(VI) for specific purposes. Cr(VI) is formed, together with the less toxic trivalent chromium (Cr(III)), when welding metals containing Cr, such as stainless steel. Management of Cr(VI) formed during the welding process is achieved by compliance with occupational exposure limit values (OELs). The recent binding OEL set under EU Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (CMD, EC, 2017) is 0.010 mg/m³ for a period of 5 years after the date of transposition of the directive; after that period a limit of 0.005 mg/m³ will apply. For welding or plasma-cutting processes or similar work processes that generate fumes, there is a derogation, with an OEL value of 0.025 mg/m³ until 5 years after the transposition date and after that period the limit will be 0.005 mg/m³. On the other hand, in France and the Netherlands, an OEL of 1 µg/m³ has been set for Cr(VI) in all uses. These are the most stringent OELs currently set in workplace in EU.

6.2 Current status of the chromate study under HBM4EU

6.2.1 Information materials and ethical permissions

Research plan for chromates study under HBM4EU was published as AD8.2 in December 2017. After the publication of the research plan, Cr(VI) information sheet, information leaflets to the participating companies and to workers as well as informed consent forms for companies and workers were prepared in collaboration with task 7.5. These were translated for local languages (French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish, German, Dutch and Finnish) by EEA.

Chromium information sheets (Working Safely with at different languages are published in <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/> (Additional Deliverable - Cr fact sheets; French, Finnish, German, Italian, Portuguese, Dutch and Polish).

Information leaflets to the participating companies and to workers as well as informed consent forms for companies and workers have been published (in English) as appendixes to Deliverable 7.4 (1st material for communication to participants, including informed consent, <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>). Informed Consent forms filled by the study participants will be archived for the entire study duration and not less than 5 years.

In order to collect relevant background information on possible confounding exposures and operating conditions and risk management measures in place at the workplace a questionnaire for data collection was prepared. This has been added as annex 1 to this report and will published in HBM4EU online library.

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Ethical permissions for the chromate study were applied for, and granted, by appropriate ethics boards in each participating country. Table 1 lists the ethical committees and the dates when ethical permissions have been granted.

Table 1: Ethical approvals granted for the Cr(VI) study

Country	Ethics committee	Number	Date granted
Belgium	Ethische Commissie Onderzoek UZ/KU Leuven, Belgium	EC No S61449 / BelRegNo. B322201837343	06-09-2018
Finland	Coordinating ethics committee, HUS Joint Authority, Helsinki, Finland	HUS/879/2018	26-03-2018
France	CPP Sud-Ouest	2018-A01096-49	26-09-2018
Italy	Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS)	Prot. PRE 122/18 del 15.02.2018	22-03-2018
The Netherlands	Regional Medical Ethical Committee Arnhem-Nijmegen	Dossier no. 2018-4642	03-01-2019
Poland	Bioethical Committee at the Nofer Institute of Occupational Medicine	Resolution No 07/2018	30-05-2018
Portugal	Ethical Committee from Lisbon School of Health Technology (ESTeSL) Ethical Committee for Health (INSA)	CE-ESTeSL -Nº. 02-2018	10-05-2018
			12-12-2018
UK	The University of Sheffield Medical School	HSL27	30-08-2018

6.2.2 Standard operating procedures

To collect comparable data in a harmonised way, great efforts were made to develop Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for the collection, handling, sample storage and transfer for each of the biological and industrial hygiene samples covered within the Cr(VI) occupational study. This work started in February 2018 and continued until the end of 2018 since some of the SOPs were identified as requiring some refining and clarification efforts after the first samplings in November 2018.

The developed SOPs aim to minimise all the factors that may lead to misrepresentation of the results and are designed considering the pre-analytical phase as a part of the laboratory work. The list of SOPs is given in Table 2 and they will be published in HBM4EU on-line library www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/. In addition to the SOPs specific for the chromate study, the participating countries must follow the general HBM4EU sample transfer protocol and SOPs for the shipment of samples when they are sent from one laboratory to another (published in www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/)

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Table 2: List of detailed SOPs prepared for the study

SOP No.	Title	Topic / Sampling matrix
1	Standard operating procedure for selection of participants and recruitment, information to the participants, informed consent	Recruitment and consent
2	Standard operating procedure for completion of company and worker questionnaires	Company and worker questionnaires
3	Standard operating procedure for blood sampling, including sample storage and transfer	Blood
4	Standard operating procedure for the collection of exhaled breath condensate samples	EBC
5	Standard operating procedure for urine sampling, including sample storage and transfer	Urine
6	Standard operating procedure for air sampling of inhalable and respirable dust fraction and (hexavalent) chromium	Air
7	Standard operating procedure for obtaining dermal wipe samples	Dermal
8	Procedure for comparing occupational hygiene measurements with exposure estimates generated using exposure models	Contextual exposure determinant information

SOP8 describes a procedure for comparing occupational hygiene measurements with exposure estimates generated using exposure models. This is a “spin-off” study, which will bring useful information especially for REACH authorisation process on the usefulness and validity of modelling methods commonly used in REACH context in chromate applications. Seven countries (UK, Belgium, Finland, Portugal, France, Italy, The Netherlands) participate in this part of the study.

6.2.3 Training school

In collaboration with WP2, a training course “HBM in occupational health: applications to chromium” was organised at 22nd of June in Ljubljana as part of the 1st HBM4EU training school. The course content and evaluation of such course has been reported as part of the 1st review of training methods (D2.6). For chromate study participants the training school provided an opportunity to discuss e.g. on the challenges related to the new methods for chromium biomonitoring.

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6.2.4 Sampling

Sampling started in many of the countries in the end of 2018 (Table 3). In the beginning of February 2019, all the other countries, except the Netherlands have started sampling (Italy started on the 11th of February). Number of companies visited and the number of biological samples collected by 1st of February have been listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Samples collected by the beginning of February 2019 in different countries

Country	Starting date for samplings	Estimated end date for samplings	No of companies visited for the collection of samples by 1.2.2019	Number of worker U-Cr/B-Cr/EBC-Cr samples collected by 1.2.2019	Comments
Belgium	1.11.2018	31.3.2019	2	46/46/46	A total of 5 companies will be sampled.
Finland	1.11.2018	31.3.2019	7	34/28/24	
France	12.10.2018	15.3.2019	6	43/38/41	
Italy	11.02.2019	31.03.2019	0	0/0/0	
The Netherlands	11.03.2019	30-11-2019	0	0/0/0	2 companies confirmed and 2 other companies expected to participate
Poland	21.11.2018	28.02.2019	3	38/38/0	
Portugal	16.1.2019	31.3.2019	(2)*	0 Planned to start the sampling campaigns on 11 February.	*Contextual information has been collected and workers have been informed about the study.
UK	12.11.2018	30.04.2019	1	10/0/10	

6.2.5 Analysis of the samples

Partners have been able to start the analysis of the industrial hygiene samples (for which no ICI/EQUAS program is established under HBM4EU) immediately after the samplings.

Five laboratories have set up the methodology for the analysis of EBC-Cr(VI). These laboratories are HSL, ISS, INRS, FIOH and KuLeuven. Poland does not collect EBC samples since they do not have the sampling device. For EBC-Cr(VI) HSL has established a small-scale interlaboratory

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comparison to ensure the quality of the analysis. This has been performed in January/February 2019 and a further round is planned for February/March 2019.

Analysis of the blood and urine samples collected by this far waits for the completion of the ICI for chromium. ICI/EQUAS for chromium has been delayed due to the resignation of the organiser. Also the analysis of the PFAS samples waits for the completion of the PFAS QA round and negotiations with the potential laboratories interested to analyse these samples.

It is planned to analyse other metals as well as Cr, especially nickel (Ni) and/or manganese (Mn) from the samples of welders and those surface treatment workers who are also performing Ni surface treatment. This can be easily done together with Cr analysis when using ICP-MS methods. These analyses can give additional, EU relevant information on the exposure of these welders and surface treatment workers. As concerns Ni, there are plans to set a binding occupational limit value in EU and the exposure information collected on Ni may support decision making at EU level. It should be, however, noted that Ni (or Mn) are not included in interlaboratory exercises under HBM4EU and therefore HBM4EU project cannot assure the comparability of these results.

Chromate study includes also collection of the samples for several effect biomarkers analyses. These analyses are made mainly with the participants own funding. INSA has some PMs for the analysis of micronuclei in peripheral blood lymphocyte micronuclei under WP14. The characterisation of effect biomarkers allows to associate the exposure to Cr(VI) with its potential impact on human health, given that they comprise sensitive endpoints that reflect early biochemical changes (subclinical changes) before the onset of disease. Effect biomarkers could be useful in the risk assessment of several toxic metals, including Cr(VI) and they may indicate combined effects of different substances, like Cr(VI) and nickel in welding. Table 4 lists the effect markers that are being analysed in the chromate study.

Table 4: Effect markers planned to be analysed in chromate study

Effect marker	Institute performing the analyses
Reticulocyte MN	FIOH
MN in PBLs	INSA/IMI
Comet assay in leukocytes	INSA/ESTeSL
Global methylation analysis (and specific epigenetic markers if pertinent)	KuLeuven
Telomer length in blood. Metabolomics studies (urine)	NIOM
Oxidative stress biomarkers in urine (8-Isoprostan to be developed)	INRS

Figure 1 gives an overall visualisation of the whole chromate study and the sample types collected in the study. The current phase of the study is sampling phase, although some samples (e.g. industrial hygiene samples) have been already analysed.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the chromate study.

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7 Identification of the substances for next occupational study

7.1 Scientific Reviews on occupational HBM studies

For the focusing of the next targeted occupational study, partners involved in the occupational group working under WP8 have made systematic reviews on occupational exposure to following substances:

- diisocyanates (2nd priority group)
- phthalates (1st priority group)
- bisphenols (1st priority group)
- PAHs (1st priority group)

The main aims of these reviews are:

- 1) To identify if we have enough data on the occupational exposure assessed through biological monitoring in relevant work sectors in EU, in which exposure to these substances may occur on the basis of their known uses
- 2) To identify the sectors which haven't been covered by measured data, or other data gaps concerning workers' exposure

These scientific reviews have been started in 2018 and are planned to be finished by mid-March 2019. The results of these reviews will guide future research plan, tentatively focused on construction and plastics sectors where exposure to the above-mentioned chemicals can occur. Systematic searches to retrieve articles suitable to be included in these reviews have been conducted following PRISMA methodology. Agreed criteria were also adopted for the study quality assessment, which was evaluated according to the LaKind score adapted to the evaluated substances therefore allowing the plan for their publication in scientific indexed papers. Annex 2 describes as an example a work-flows used for phthalates and diisocyanates and the criteria which have been used to assess the study quality in the case of these substances.

Although no final conclusions are available yet, the following initial conclusions can be made on the basis of the work done by this far.

7.1.1 Phthalates

The systematic search was carried out on Pubmed, Scopus, and Isi Web of Science databases according to the PRISMA guidelines for articles published between 2000 and 31 October 2018. Twenty-two studies focusing on Human Biomonitoring of phthalates in occupational settings, and 27 studies on analytical methods were identified and considered suitable for review. As concerns the type of phthalate exposure, out of 22 studies on Human Biomonitoring, 19 (86%) regarded DEHP, which is subjected to authorisation and restriction. Only two studies were focused on occupational exposure to new phthalates, such as DINCH, DINP, DPHP. Only one of these was performed in Europe, Germany, on plastisol workers that showed post shift values of DiNP and DiDP metabolites approximately 20-times higher, and pre-shift values approximately 5–10 times higher than those of the general background exposure (Koch et al., 2012). Regarding countries in which such investigations were performed, from the 22 Human Biomonitoring studies, 8 have been performed in Asia, 5 in America and 9 in Europe. Particularly, the European distribution was the following: 5 studies in Slovakia, 2 in France, 1 in Germany and 1 in the Netherlands. Most of HBM studies have been performed in plastic industries (13 papers); the others were in waste management (3), in cosmetics (3), in cleaning (1), in dental laboratory (1) and in flavoring plant (1). Future studies should focus on new phthalates and substitutes but not forgetting old ones e.g. in waste management or recycling (which has not been studied before). It is also evident the need to include some other occupational sectors, such as the production of waterproof gloves, tablecloths,

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shower curtains, floor tiles, toys as well as waste sorting to future research works. Overall, our findings indicate that there is a lack of recent occupational HBM studies in European countries and considering that important policy actions were taken in Europe, it is of most relevance to evaluate the impact of these actions on workers exposure.

7.1.2 Bisphenols

Although there are data on the exposure to bisphenol A in different fields (30 occupational studies selected according to PRISMA methodology), occupational exposure to other bisphenol compounds (i.e. bisphenol S and bisphenol F) is limited. In fact, among the 65 articles given by our literature search only two of them describe the exposure assessment of workers to BPS and these were related to thermal receipts. From the two studies only one has been carried out in Europe (i.e. France). No studies on occupational exposure to BPF have been reported (among the 11 articles selected) highlighting the lack of data.

At first sight, there is a need to bridge the gap in terms of exposure assessment to BPA analogs in order to acquire data at European level and improve risk assessment. This is of particular relevance since regulatory actions were taken to reduce BPA but an increase was observed in the use and applications of BPS and BPF.

7.1.3 Diisocyanates

A literature search was conducted from year 2000 onwards in PubMed and Web of Science, using the following search terms for MDI, HDI and TDI: (“Occupational” OR “worker*”) AND (“biomonitor*” OR “biomarker*” OR “urin*”). The chemical names were also spelled out. About 160 publications were retrieved (Figure 1). Studies were subsequently evaluated (independently by two reviewers) based on the abstract and were excluded if: published in a language other than English, contained no biomonitoring information or were conducted in animals. Review papers were screened for potential additional studies which were not retrieved via the systematic review. This left us with about 77 studies which were ranking independently by two reviewers using a modified version of the Lakind scoring criteria (Table 1). This review process is still ongoing but is expected to be ready before the end of March 2019. A next step would then be to evaluate and summarise, based on the retrieved studies, which biomonitoring data for diisocyanates is available, and whether certain sectors have not yet been covered in terms of biomonitoring data collection. A first glance on the studies gives the impression that mainly exposure in the polyurethane manufacturing industry has been investigated, but studies were also retrieved on diisocyanate biomonitoring data from workers in the motor vehicle repair or paint industry. There is a need to investigate this further because concerns have been raised that exposure to diisocyanates at small and medium sized enterprises is a particular problem.

7.1.4 PAHs

Thirty occupational HBM studies on PAHs were selected according to PRISMA method. These studies were published after 2008 and were reporting exposure in sites located in European countries. Most of the studies were focused on occupational settings where exposure is known to be high, such as bitumen workers and road-side construction and coke plant, aluminum electrode production plant and coal tar use. From 30 studies, 10 were developed in Germany and 3 in France and the rest are distributed in several countries such as Italy, Spain, Poland, Finland, Slovakia, Portugal, the Netherlands and Czech Republic. There appears to be a trend for the use of the urinary metabolite 1-OHP (18 (64%) studies present 1-OHP data), probably because it still represents the best biomarker of occupational exposure to PAHs (SCOEL 2016). However, it should be pointed out that for evaluation of low-level occupational exposure to PAHs, it is crucial to consider intra- and inter-individual background variation in the evaluation of 1-OHP. This explains

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why most of the studies used a control group or used two sampling moments (pre and post-shift, and sometimes during several days of the working week).

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8 References

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9 Annexes

9.1 Annex 1: Chromate study questionnaire for workplaces and workers

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR WORKPLACES (self-administered)

We would be grateful if you can complete this short questionnaire concerning your companies' activities relating to hexavalent chromium and other chemicals. Please return it directly to the researcher once completed.

Company and Occupational Health care information

Name and position of the company representative:

Name of the Company/Organisation:

Name of the department:

Site address:

Country:

Industrial sector:

NACE Rev.2 code (to be filled by researcher):

Description of the workplace (nature of the business, what is being manufactured, how the work is organized):

.....

Describe the general training, monitoring, and occupational health and safety practices related to exposure to hazardous chemicals in your company:

.....

Name and address of the Occupational health care:

.....

Contact person and contact details (e-mail, phone number) of the Occupational Health and Safety department:

.....

Operational conditions

k. The frequency of cadmium plating operations? (categories: daily, days/week or days/month)

l. Size of the parts treated? (please describe)

m. How many employees work on these activities?

Risk management measures for chrome plating (please circle)

Enclosure of the bath			Total	Partial
No				
Local exhaust ventilation (LEV) present at bath	Yes	No		
Use of bubble dispersers on the liquid surface	Yes	No		
The use of mist suppressants			Yes	No
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ PFAS (Perfluoroalkylated substances) suppressant use 	Yes (please specify)	No	Don't know	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Other suppressant use 	Yes (please specify)	No		

2. Surface treatment by spraying or painting

a. Used quantities of hexavalent chromium in % the paint? (please tick box)

≤0.01; >0.01-0.1; >0.1-0.5; >0.5-1; >1-5; >5-10; >10-15; >15 %

b. Average quantity of paint used per month (litres or gallons)? litres / gallons

c. Frequency of spraying or painting and machining operations? (categories: daily, weekly, monthly, other)

d. Size of the parts sprayed or painted? (please describe)

e. How many employees work on these activities?

3. Welding

a. The frequency of welding operations? (categories: daily, weekly, monthly, other)

b. Size of the parts welded? (please describe)

c. How many employees work on these activities?

What welding method is used? (please tick box)	<input type="checkbox"/> MMA (manual metal arc) <input type="checkbox"/> MAG (metal active gas) <input type="checkbox"/> MIG (metal inert gas) <input type="checkbox"/> TIG (tungsten inert gas) <input type="checkbox"/> SAW (submerged arc welding) <input type="checkbox"/> Plasma - plasma gas <input type="checkbox"/> Flux-cored welding <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/>
--	---

4. Previous measurements

Have any of the following types of measurements been collected from your workers at the site?

Measurements	Tick all that apply	Years collected
Air samples	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Dermal exposure measurements	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Blood samples from workers	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Urine samples from workers	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Other (please specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Would you be willing to allow the researchers to have access to these results (in a confidential manner)? (Please circle) Yes No

If yes, contact person and contact details (e-mail, phone number):

Thank you for filling the questionnaire!

Please return it directly to the researcher once completed.

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POST-SHIFT QUESTIONNAIRE FOR WORKERS (interviewed by researcher)

Background information about worker

Worker ID	
Urine sample	Date collected: _____ Time: _____ Sample code: _____
EBC sample	Date collected: _____ Time: _____ Sample code: _____
Blood sample	Date collected: _____ Time: _____ Sample code: _____
Air sample (personal)	Date collected: _____ Sample code: _____
Wipe sample(s) (personal)	Date collected: _____ Sample code(s): _____
Company name and name of department	
Worker name and position	
Sex (please circle)	Male _____ Female _____
Date of birth (dd/mm/yyyy)	

Please separate this sheet from the Questionnaire

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Cigarette smoking (continues)	Approximate number of cigarettes/day Number of years you have smoked If former smoker, how many years ago did you stop smoking? Approximate number of cigarettes/day you smoked Number of years you smoked
Worker ID	
Do you smoke electronic cigarettes? (please circle)	Yes No Former e-cigarette
E-cigarettes (continues)	Approximate number of e-cigarettes/day Number of years you have smoked e-cigarettes If former e-cigarettes smoker, how many year ago did you stop smoking? Approximate number of e-cigarettes/day you smoked Number of years you smoked e-cigarettes
Do you use any other tobacco products? (please circle)	Yes No Former user If yes or former user, please specify
Other tobacco products (continues)	Approximate number of tobacco product/day Number of years you have used If former user, how many years ago did you stop? Approximate number of product/day you used Number of years used
Do you have implants which may contain metals, e.g. pins, rods, screws, plates, hip, knee joints etc? (please circle)	Yes No Don't know If yes, how long is it since they were implanted? Do you know what type of implants? (please specify)
Do you have dental fillings? (please circle)	Yes No If yes, do you know what material they are made? (please specify)

During the past 3 months, have you had a medical x-ray or Computerised Axial Tomography (CAT) scan? (please circle)	Yes No
Worker ID	
Have you previously, or are you currently, being treated for cancer? (please circle)	Yes No
Alcohol consumption	Yes No How often do you typically drink alcohol? (please circle) daily weekly monthly
Alcohol consumption (continues)	On average, how many days in a month do you have at least one alcoholic beverage? On a typical day that you drink alcohol, how many drinks do you usually have?
Consumption of other beverages (please circle)	Coffee Tea Energy drinks On average, how many times in a typical day? Coffee Tea Energy drinks
Dietary habits (please circle)	Mixed Vegetarian Vegan Other (please specify)
Use of food supplements (e.g. diet pills) (please circle)	Yes No If yes, please specify:
Recreational activities or hobbies which may cause additional chromate exposure (e.g. welding, paint spraying, metal works) (please circle)	Yes No If yes, please specify:

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Occupational history

Worker ID	Did the work involve any of the following activities (tick that apply)				Start time (year)	Finish time (year)
Occupation/job title	metal plating	painting or spraying	welding	other metal works		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Job description

What job were you doing today?

Job	(Tick if apply)	Complete questions in Section
Chrome plating	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Spraying/painting	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Welding	<input type="checkbox"/>	3

1. Job description in chrome plating in baths (please list the type of work tasks you have been involved in today)

Worker ID	Work task	Duration of the task in a work shift (hours/minutes)	Frequency of the task (x times per week)	Process type (manual or automatic)	PPE* used (add the corresponding numbers)	LEV** used (yes, no)
1	Readjustment of the electrolyte: decanting and weighing, mixing, re-filling of baths					
2	Application in baths: loading of jigs, chemical pre-treatment, application by dipping or immersion, rinsing and drying, chemical post treatment, cleaning and unloading of jigs, cleaning of equipment, regular maintenance of equipment					
3	Infrequent maintenance activities					
4	Drawing of sample and transfer to laboratory					
5	Laboratory analysis					
6	Waste management					
7	Other (please specify)					

*PPE (Personal protective equipment) worn:

1. Powered or air-fed, filtering respirator
2. Reusable half or full face mask respirator (without powered or air-fed respirator)
3. Disposable face mask
4. Other Respiratory Protection Equipment (please specify)
5. Coveralls
6. Reusable Gloves
7. Disposable gloves
8. Other (please specify)

** LEV=local exhaust ventilation

Has your respiratory protection equipment (mask) been fit tested? (please circle)	Yes If yes, when?	No
Have you received information, instruction or training on the use of safe work practices	Yes	No

when carrying out this activity? (please circle)	If yes, when?
Hygiene facilities in the company (please tick box if apply)	<input type="checkbox"/> Possibility to wash hands <input type="checkbox"/> Take shower <input type="checkbox"/> Separate place for working clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Specific place for the storage of respiratory protective equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)..... <input type="checkbox"/>
Have the work conditions been normal during the work day? (please circle)	Yes No If not normal, please specify (e.g. problems with mask or extraction not working):

2. Job description in surface treatment by spraying or painting (please list the type of work tasks you have been involved in today)

	Worker ID				
	Work task	Duration of the task in a work shift (hours/minutes)	Frequency of the task (x times per week)	PPE* used (add the corresponding numbers)	LEV** used (yes, no)
1	Preparation tasks: Decanting, Mixing of paints, Re-filling of apparatus				
2	Spraying in spray cabin/spray booth				
3	Spraying outside of spray booth				
4	Surface treatment in automatic spray tunnel				
5	Surface treatment by rolling (small to medium sized areas)				
6	Surface treatment by brushing or pen stick (small areas/touch-up)				
7	Drying/self-curing (activities of workers outside one meter distance to the drying part) with no LEV				
8	Cleaning and maintenance of equipment				
9	Infrequent maintenance activities				

3. Job description in welding (please list the type of work tasks you have been involved in today)

Worker ID				
Work task	Duration of the task in a work shift (hours/minutes)	Frequency of the task (x times per week)	PPE* used (add the corresponding numbers)*	LEV** used: 1. Gun fixed extraction 2. Movable welding hood 3. Extracted work bench 4. Extracted welding booth 5. General ventilation 6. Other (please specify)
1	Manual welding			
2	Manual tack-welding			
3	Robot welding			
4	Other manual tasks: Cleaning, Grinding, Cutting etc.			
5	Cleaning and maintenance of equipment			
6	Waste management			
7	Other (please specify)			

*PPE (Personal protective equipment) worn:

1. Welding helmet with powered or air-fed, filtering respirator
2. Welding helmet with half mask re-usable dust respirator
3. Welding helmet with disposable particulate respirator
4. Welding helmet without any respirator
5. Welding helmet with other respiratory protection equipment (please specify)
6. Fire/flame resistant clothing
7. Welding gloves
8. Other gloves
9. Other (please specify)

** LEV=local exhaust ventilation

Has your respiratory protection equipment (mask) been fit tested? (please circle)	Yes	No
	If yes, when?	

Have you received information, instruction or training on the use of safe work practices when carrying out this activity? (please circle)	Yes If yes, when?	No
Hygiene facilities in the company (please tick box if apply)	<input type="checkbox"/> Possibility to wash hands <input type="checkbox"/> Take shower <input type="checkbox"/> Separate place for working clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Specific place for the storage of respiratory protective equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)..... <input type="checkbox"/>	
Have the work conditions been normal during the work day? (please circle)	Yes If not normal, please specify (e.g. problems with mask or extraction not working):	No

Operational conditions in welding

Worker ID	
What material was welded? (please circle)	Stainless steel Other (please specify)
Chromium and nickel content of the welded material?	Chromium content:% Nickel content:% Don't know (please circle if apply)
What welding method was used? (please tick box)	<input type="checkbox"/> MMA (manual metal arc) <input type="checkbox"/> MAG (metal active gas) <input type="checkbox"/> MIG (metal inert gas) <input type="checkbox"/> TIG (tungsten inert gas) <input type="checkbox"/> SAW (submerged arc welding) <input type="checkbox"/> Plasma - plasma gas <input type="checkbox"/> Flux-cored welding <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)..... <input type="checkbox"/>
For gas welding, what gas mixture was used? e.g. 97.5% argon and 2.5% CO ₂	Don't know (please circle if apply)

Was the welded material painted? (please circle)	Yes No Don't know
Was it a chromium containing paint? (please circle)	Yes No Don't know
What were the welding voltage and current used?	Voltage: V Current: A Don't know (please circle if apply)
Material and type of the welding rod?	 Don't know (please circle if apply)
Material of the welding flux?	 Don't know (please circle if apply)
Where do you weld? (please tick box if apply)	<input type="checkbox"/> Outdoor <input type="checkbox"/> Indoor in a space >1000 m3 <input type="checkbox"/> Indoor in a confined space of m3 <input type="checkbox"/> with no/natural ventilation <input type="checkbox"/> with forced ventilation (e.g. ship building) <input type="checkbox"/> with LEV*
During welding did you need to position your head in the fume plume? (please tick box if apply)	<input type="checkbox"/> Almost always, i.e. more than 90% arc time <input type="checkbox"/> Often, i.e. more than half the arc time <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes, i.e. less than half arc time <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never, i.e. <10% of arc time
Worker ID	

* LEV=local exhaust ventilation

9.2 Annex 2: Phthalates and Diisocyanates, work-flow for the selection of the relevant papers and LaKind criteria adapted for phthalates for the assessment of the quality of the selected papers

Flowchart of search strategy and selection of studies, on phthalate exposure and biomonitoring data, for inclusion in review.

Flowchart of search strategy and selection of studies, on diisocyanate exposure and biomonitoring data, for inclusion in review.

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Tables: Adaptation of LaKind scoring criteria for a) phthalates b) diisocyanate reviews

Assessment component	TIER 1 (most relevant)	TIER 2 (relevant)	TIER 3 (not so relevant)
Study type	Occupational	Volunteer exposure study	Environmental exposure
Study participants	>20 exposed individuals	5-20 exposed individuals	<5 exposed individuals
Chemicals under investigation	Currently used phthalates or substitutes (DINP, DPHP, DIDP, DINCH)	older, authorized/restricted phthalates (DBP, DEHP....)	Phthalates with no use in Europe (not registered, no known current or past uses in Europe)
Exposure biomarker and matrix	Biomarker in a specified matrix has accurate and precise quantitative relationship with external exposure, internal dose, or target dose.	Evidence exists for a relationship between biomarker in a specified matrix and external exposure, internal dose, or target dose.	Biomarker in a specified matrix is a poor surrogate (low accuracy and precision) for exposure/dose.
Biological effect marker (if applicable)	Bioindicator of a key event in an adverse outcome pathway (AOP).	Biomarkers of effect shown to have a relationship to health outcomes but the mechanism of action is not understood.	Biomarker has undetermined consequences (e.g., biomarker is not specific to a health outcome).
Biomarker specificity	Biomarker is derived from exposure to one parent chemical.	Biomarker is derived from multiple parent chemicals with similar adverse endpoints.	Biomarker is derived from multiple parent chemicals with varying types of adverse endpoints.
Technique	Instrumentation that provides unambiguous identification and quantitation of the biomarker at the required sensitivity (e.g., GC-HRMS, GC-MS/MS, LC-MS/MS).	Instrumentation that allows for identification of the biomarker with a high degree of confidence and the required sensitivity (e.g., GC-MS, GC-ECD).	Instrumentation that only allows for possible quantification of the biomarker but the method has known interferants (e.g., GC-FID, spectroscopy).

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Assessment component	TIER 1 (most relevant)	TIER 2 (relevant)	TIER 3 (not so relevant)
Method characteristics – <i>Any specific weaknesses in study design leading to a TIER 3 score to be noted.</i>	Acceptable limit of detection (LoD)		LoD above current state-of-the-art
	Samples with a known history and documented stability data or those using real-time measurements.	Stability not specifically assessed, but samples were stored appropriately and analysed promptly.	Specific reason to query stability. E.g. samples with unknown history or known issues.
	Samples are contamination-free from time of collection to time of measurement (e.g., by use of certified analyte-free collection supplies and reference materials, and appropriate use of blanks both in the field and lab). Research includes documentation of the steps taken to provide the necessary assurance that the study data are reliable.	Study not using/documenting these procedures.	There are known contamination issues and no documentation that the issues were addressed.
Quality assurance	Study has used external QA where appropriate	Some QA used (note details)	No QA
Matrix adjustment and sampling strategy	Study includes results for adjusted and non-adjusted concentrations if adjustment is needed. 24 h total urine collection or spot samples in different moments. e.g. pre and post shift. is considered tier 1.	Study only provides results using one method (matrix-adjusted or not). And single spot urine sample per individual taken in a defined sampling time, which can be considered valid when taking into account the toxicokinetics of the biomarker.	No established method for adjustment (e.g., adjustment for hair) Sampling time unclear or not valid (i.e. sample taken too long after the cessation of occupational exposure).

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Assessment component	TIER 1	TIER 2	TIER 3
Study participants	>20 occupationally exposed individuals	5-20 occupationally exposed individuals	Any other study (<5 occupationally exposed individuals, volunteers, general population)
Chemicals under investigation	HDI, TDI and/or MDI	IPDI, NDI	Any other isocyanates
Exposure biomarker and matrix	Biomarker in a specified matrix has accurate and precise quantitative relationship with external exposure, internal dose, or target dose e.g. diamines, Hb-adducts	Evidence exists for a relationship between biomarker in a specified matrix and external exposure, internal dose, or target dose but limited application e.g. other protein adducts or conjugates	Biomarker in a specified matrix is a poor surrogate (low accuracy and precision) for exposure/dose e.g. experimental biomarkers, non-specific markers such as general effect markers
Biomarker specificity	Biomarker is derived from exposure to one parent chemical.	Biomarker is derived from multiple parent chemicals with similar adverse endpoints.	Biomarker is derived from multiple parent chemicals with varying types of adverse endpoints.
Technique	Instrumentation that provides unambiguous identification and quantitation of the biomarker at the required sensitivity (e.g., GC-HRMS, GC-MS/MS, LC-MS/MS).	Instrumentation that allows for identification of the biomarker with a high degree of confidence and the required sensitivity (e.g., GC-MS, GC-ECD).	Instrumentation that only allows for possible quantification of the biomarker but the method has known interferants (e.g., GC-FID, spectroscopy).
Method characteristics – Any specific weaknesses in study design leading to a TIER 3 score to be noted.	Acceptable LoD		LoD above current state-of –the-art
	Samples with a known history and documented stability data or those using real-time measurements.	Stability not specifically assessed, but samples were stored appropriately and analysed promptly.	Specific reason to query stability. E.g. samples with unknown history or known issues.

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Assessment component	TIER 1	TIER 2	TIER 3
	<p>Samples are contamination-free from time of collection to time of measurement (e.g., by use of certified analyte-free collection supplies and reference materials, and appropriate use of blanks both in the field and lab). Research includes documentation of the steps taken to provide the necessary assurance that the study data are reliable.</p>	<p>Study not using/documenting these procedures.</p>	<p>There are known contamination issues and no documentation that the issues were addressed.</p>